

Taxonomy notes (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)

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Abstract: *Cleroclytus* (*Obliqueclytus*, **subgen. n.**) is described with the type species: *Anaglyptus banghaasi* Reitter, 1895. *Anoplistes halodendri kasatkini*, **ssp. n.** is described from Dagestan. *Cleroclytus collaris savitskyi*, **ssp. n.** is described from Mongolia. *Brachyta variabilis shapovalovi*, **ssp. n.** is described from East Kazakhstan. *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *cinerarium papayense*, **ssp. n.** is described from Papay Mountain in Krasnodar Region. *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *gorbunovi rubenyani*, **ssp. n.** is described from Armenia. *Stromatium auratum* (Böber, 1793), **nom. rest.** is introduced as a valid name for the species, which is known now as “*Stromatium unicolor* Olivier, 1795”, but traditionally as “*Stromatium fulvum* (Villers, 1789)”. New locality records are proposed for: *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *sisianense* Lazarev, 2009, *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *megriense* Lazarev, 2009, *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *laeve vladimiri* Danilevsky et Murzin, 2009, *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *indutum* Faldennann, 1837. *Dorcadion guzeldereense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2013 and *Dorcadion karacaorenense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2013 are declared to be unjustified emendations (available names). Valid names are *Dorcadion guzeldereense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2012 and *Dorcadion karacaorenense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2012. The real absence of antennal setae tufts in *Agapanthia dahli calculensis* Lazarev, 2013 is demonstrated.

Several abbreviations are used in the text:

MD - collection of M. Danilevsky, Moscow

ML - collection of M. Lazarev, Moscow

RF - collection of R. Filimonov, Sankt-Petersburg

ZIN - Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences,
Sankt-Petersburg

ZMM - Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Moscow

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Brachyta variabilis shapovalovi, ssp. n.

(Figs 1-2)

Type locality. East Kazakhstan Region, Kokpekty environs (48°44'54''N, 82°24'53''E), 500 m.

Diagnosis. The taxon is characterized by wide body, very dense elytral punctation, stable elytral design, red legs and antennae.

Head with dense, partly conjugated fine punctation and dense short yellowish pubescence; base of clypeus can be strongly concaved; male antennae reaching elytral middle, female antennae never surpassing anterior elytral third; antennal joints short and thick; outer angles of 6-10th male antennal joints distinctly projected laterally, much stronger than in female; 11th joint with well developed appendage; 3rd joint about as long as 1st, longer than 5th, and much longer than 4th; all joints covered with fine short yellowish pubescence; prothorax in males as long as basal width or about 1.07 times longer; in females - about 1.02-1.2 times wider than long; lateral thoracic tubercles well developed; pronotal punctation similar to the nominative subspecies; elytra wide, male elytra slightly tapering posteriorly, female elytra about parallelsided; elytral punctation very dense, interspaces often smaller than dots, with numerous fine wrinkles; elytra covered with short recumbent pubescence and scattered erect yellowish setae, more yellow than in pale forms of the nominative subspecies; body black; antennae, palpi, labrum, anterior clypeus margin, mandibles (partly), legs and 3 last abdominal sternites red or yellow-red; elytra yellow with black lines; black lines can never be brown; elytra can never be unicolor (brown or black as often in the nominative subspecies); body length in males: 12.4-14.5 mm, width: 4.4-5.4 mm; body length in females: 13.5-19.1 mm; width: 4.9-7.3 mm.

Distribution. Kazakhstan: Bolshenarymskoe, Buchtarma, Bystry Irtysh, Layly mining camp, Kokpekty, between Svinchatka and Slavyanka.

Material. Holotype, male with two labels: 1) "Kaz. SSR, Kokpekty, 500 m, 25.V.1989, leg. M. Danilevsky", 2) "Paratypus, *Brachyta variabilis oblomovi* ssp.n. A. Shapovalov det., 2007" - MD; 24 Paratypes: 1 female with same labels - MD; 1 male with two labels: 1) Kazakhstan, East Kazakhstan Region, Layly mining camp,

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11.05.1941, A. Oblomov, 2) “Holotypus, *Brachyta variabilis oblomovi* ssp.n. A. Shapovalov det., 2007” - ZMM; 9 males, 10 females, same locality, 11-13.05.1941 - ZMM; 1 female, Kazakhstan, East Kazakhstan Region, Bolshenarymskoe, 25.05.1930, F. Lukyanovich - ZMM; 1 male, Kazakhstan, East Kazakhstan Region, “between Svinchatka and Slavyanka”, 27.05.1987, V.A. Lukhtanov - RF; 1 female, “Buchtarma, 1889, Kinderm.” - ZIN; 1 female, Semipalatinsk Region, Bystry Irtysh, 03.05.1908, M. Cissobr. - ZIN.

Remarks. *Brachyta variabilis shapovalovi*, ssp. n. is close to the nominative subspecies (distributed from Altay area to about Baikal Lake), but differs by wide body, goldish dorsal pubescence, dense finely rugose elytral punctuation, always red legs and antennae, stable elytral design.

Etymology. The new subspecies is dedicated to my good friend Andrey Shapovalov, who originally separated this taxon as new.

***Stromatium auratum* (Böber, 1793), nom. rest.**

Saperda aurata Böber, 1793: 135 – “Taurien”; Löbl et Smetana 2013: 42 [“p. 334. add *Saperda aurata* Böber, 1793: 135 under nomina dubia”]; Danilevsky, 2012: 712 [“most probably the name of the species known now as *Stromatium unicolor*”].

Cerambyx fulvum Villers, 1789: 256 [HN]

Callidium unicolor Olivier, 1795: no. 70: 58.

Stromatium fulvum, Plavilstshikov, 1940: 73.

Stromatium unicolor, Löbl et Smetana, 2010: 186.

Type locality. Crimea.

A single character mentioned in the original description: “*tota aurata nitida*” together with Crimean origin of the taxon allow the exact identification of the species known before as *Stromatium unicolor* (Olivier, 1795).

Anoplistes halodendri kasatkini, ssp. n.
(Figs 3-6)

Type locality. Russia, Dagestan: Agvali (42°32'26''N, 46°7'20''E), 900 m.

Diagnosis. Male antennae are rather variable in length; three males have very short antennae just a little longer than body, surpassing elytral apices by three joints only: holotype (Fig. 3), a male from Tlokh and a male from Zovutameer Mt.; short male antennae are not known in any other subspecies of *A. halodendri*; another 2 males from Tlokh have longer antennae, which surpassing elytral apices by 4 joints (Fig. 4), and the last male from Tlokh has very long antennae which are about two times longer than body (Fig. 5) similar to the nominative subspecies; males with short antennae and a female from Zovutameer Mt. are with much darker elytra, with narrow lateral red line and two red spots near base; elytra in other males and in a female from Tlokh have wide lateral red area, which is widened anteriorly reaching elytral base, but elytral humery with black dots; body length in males: 10.8-13.5 mm, width: 2.7-3.5 mm; body length in female: 12.5-14.9 mm; width: 3.0-3.7 mm.

Distribution. Three localities are known in Dagestan: Agvali (42°32'26''N, 46°7'20''E), 900 m; Tlokh (42°40'37''N, 42°40'37''E), 500-1000 m; Nukatl Ridge, NW slope of Zovutameer Mountain.

Material. Holotype, male with two labels: 1) "S Russia, Dagestan, Agvali, 22.6.1983, A.Birshtein leg.", 2) "Paratypus, *Asias montanus* sp.n., det. Kasatkin D.G. 2001" - MD; 7 paratypes: 4 males and 1 female, Dagestan, Tlokh, 500-1000 m, 24.05-03.06.1988, V.Karasev - MD, ZMM; 1 male and 1 female, each with two labels: 1) [„Dagestan, Nukatl Ridge, NW slope of Zovutameer Mountain, 29.07.1997, A. Gusakov][in Russian], 2) "Paratypus, *Asias montanus* sp.n., det. Kasatkin D.G. 2001"- ZMM.

Etymology. The subspecies is dedicated to Dr. Denis Kasatkin (Rostov-on-Don), who originally separated this taxon as a new species.

Remarks. The specimens designated by D. Kasatkin as paratypes of *Asias montanus* were never published.

Anoplistes halodendri kasatkini, ssp. n. is very close to

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A. h. ephippium (Steven & Dalman, 1817), but differs by much darker elytra and by the presence of the males with short antennae in population.

Cleroclytus (Obliqueclytus, subgen. n.)

Type species: *Anaglyptus banghaasi* Reitter, 1895

The subgenus is characterized by oblique “S”-shaped elytral pale bar, while in the nominative subgenus pale elytral bar is always transverse, curved anteriorly or straight and slightly inclined - in *C. (s. str.) francottei* Rapuzzi & Sama, 2010.

The new subgenus includes 2 species: *C. (O.) banghaasi* (Reitter, 1895) and *C. (O.) gracilis* Jakovlev, 1900.

The nominative subgenus also consists of 2 species *C. (s. str.) francottei* Rapuzzi & Sama, 2010 and *C. (s. str.) semirufus* Kraatz, 1884 with two subspecies: *C. (s. str.) s. semirufus* Kraatz, 1884 and *C. (s. str.) s. collaris* Jakovlev, 1885.

C. (s. str.) francottei Rapuzzi & Sama, 2010 described from Gansu on the base of a single male easily differs from *C. (s. str.) collaris* Jakovlev, 1885 by distinctly inclined, straight white elytral bar and oblique white setae stripe near elytral apices.

Cleroclytus (s. str.) collaris savitskyi, ssp. n.

(Figs 7-8)

Type locality. Mongolia: Kobd aimak, 44 km NNW Bulgan, Burgastyn-Ehniy-Undar Mts. S slope, 46°25′50″N 91°13′35″E.

Diagnosis. The new taxon is close to the nominative subspecies *C. c. collaris*, but strongly differs from its eastern most populations distributed around Zaisan Lake by very dark color. Prothorax and elytra are about totally black. Only hind pronotal margin can be slightly reddish and elytral area near scutellum as well. All femora are blackish, antennae are dark-red and relatively short. Male antennae surpassing elytral apices by 2 apical joints only, while male antennae in *C. c. collaris* usually overcome elytra by 3 apical joints. Longitudinal pronotal striation in the *C.c.savitskyi, ssp. n.* poorly developed and more or less distinct only anteriorly, while in eastern populations of *C. c. collaris* pronotal striae often reach hind pronotal

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margin. Besides, specimens of *C. c. collaris* from eastern Kazakhstan are very light, pronotum and anterior elytral half are often totally red. Rather black specimens of the nominative subspecies similar to *C. c. savitskyi*, **ssp. n.** are available from South Kazakhstan only (Taraz environs); body length in males: 5.4-6.6 mm, width: 1.3-1.6 mm; body length in females: 6.5-6.7 mm; width: 1.6-1.7 mm.

Distribution. Mongolia: Kobd aimak, 44 km NNW Bulgan, Burgastyn-Ehniy-Undar Mts. S slope, 46°25'50''N 91°13'35''E; Kobd aimak, 42 km NNW Bulgan, Bayan-Gol River, 46°24'05''N 91°12'50''E; Khovd aimak, 30 km NNW Bulgan, confluence of Bayan-Gol and Bulgan-Gol rivers; Khovd aimak, Dod-Narujn (right tributary of Bulgan-gol).

Material. Holotype, male, "Mongolia, Kobd aimak, 42 km NNW Bulgan, Bayan-Gol River, 1600 m, 6-8.7.2013, 46°24'05''N 91°12'50''E, V. Savitsky leg." - ZMM; 4 paratypes: 1 male, Kobd aimak, 20 km N Bulgan, Ulyastayn-Gol, 01.07.1980, I. Kerzhner - ZIN; 1 male, Mongolia, Kobd aimak, 44 km NNW Bulgan, Burgastyn-Ehniy-Undar Mts. S slope, 30.6.2013, 46°25'50''N 91°13'35''E, V. Savitsky leg. - MD; 1 female, Mongolia, Khovd aimak, Dod-Narujn, 26.6.2005, (right trib. of Bulgan-gol), R. Yakovlev - ZMM; 1 female, West Mongolia, Khovd aimak, 30 km NNW Bulgan, confluence Rivers Bayan-Gol and Bulgan-Gol, 1500 m., 14.5.2002, R.V. Yakovlev - MD.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to Vladimir Savitsky, who collected two males in Mongolia.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium papayense*, **ssp. n.*

(Fig. 9)

Type locality. Russia, Krasnodar Region: Papay Mt., 600 m, 44°38'27" N, 38°23'43"E.

Diagnosis. Only one male known; prothorax with slightly sharpened lateral tubercles; pronotum glabrous, but with white narrow longitudinal setae stripe, with scattered fine punctation and distinct micropunctation; elytra with hardly visible dorsal carinae, covered by dense black pubescence with bright white suture strip and narrow white marginal stripe covering epipleurae; white humeral stripe represented by a small anterior stroke, posteriorly indistinct;

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1st antennal joint and legs red; body length: 15.7 mm, width: 5.6 mm.

Distribution. Krasnodar Region, Papay Mountains, 44°38'27" N, 38°23'43"E, 600 m, 30 km E Gelendzhik.

Material. Holotype, 1 male, "Krasnodar Reg., 600 m, Papay Mt. [44°38'27" N, 38°23'43"E.], 30 km E Gelendzhik, 7.5.2010, E. Khomitsky leg." - MD.

Etymology. Papay Mountain is the type locality of the taxon.

Remarks. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium papayense* ssp.n. is close to *D. (C.) c. veniamini* Lazarev, 2011 geographically and because of its very big size (the biggest known subspecies), besides thoracic tubercles are rather similar, but elytra in *D. (C.) c. veniamini* are always totally glabrous in males, pronotum with dense rough punctation, with less pronounced micropunctation in the middle, elytral carinae obliterated.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) gorbunovi rubenyani, ssp. n.

(Figs 10-11)

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) gorbunovi, Danilevsky. 2010: 247, part. - Armenia, Azerbaijan.

Type locality. Armenia: Svarantz, 39°21'21''N 46°12'27''E, 1880 m.

Diagnosis. Only 6 males and 2 females known; pronotum glabrous, without white line, with dense irregular, conjugated, rugose punctation, with smooth, shining areas in the middle, with distinct micropunctation; elytra with dense grey pubescence and wide humeral black stripe, white stripes absent as in the nominative subspecies; sometimes two short black strokes present near base; body length in males: 12.4-15.1 mm, width: 4.8-5.6 mm; body length in females: 14.3-16.1 mm; width: 5.4-6.6 mm.

Distribution. All localities mentioned by collectors are most probably connected with one population. Armenia: Svarantz 39°21'21''N, 46°12'27''E, 1880 m; 1 km S Svarantz, 1917 m, 39°21'13''N, 46°12'44''E; Tatev (39°24'11''N, 46°13'55''E) environs.

Material. Holotype, male, "Armenia, Svarantz, 1880 m, 39°21'21''N 46°12'27''E, 04.05.2013, A. Rubenyan" - MD;

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7 Paratypus: 4 males, same label - MD, ML; 1 female, Armenia, 1 km S Svarantz, 1917 m, 39°21'13''N 46°12'44''E, 14.05.2011, A. Rubenyan” - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Armenia, Tatev, 21.05.1988, M. Kalashyan - MD.

Dedication. The new taxon is dedicated to well known insect collector Artem Rubenyan, who collected the most part of the type series.

Remarks. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) gorbunovi rubenyani*, **ssp. n.** differs from *D. (C.) g. gorbunovi* by more elongated shape of bigger body; less regular pronotal punctation and bigger lateral pronotal tubercles; the biggest male of *D. g. gorbunovi* is 12.0 mm and the biggest known female is 13.7 mm among several hundreds of studied specimens.

The nominative subspecies is known from Nakhichevan Republic of Azerbaijan only. All *D. gorbunovi* Danilevsky, 1985 from Armenia belong to the new subspecies. Armenian populations were known from long ago, but traditionally included in the nominative subspecies (Danilevsky, 2010).

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) guzeldereense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2012**

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) guzeldereense Bernhauer & Peks, 2012: 213 [wrong original spelling - Art. 11.2.]

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) guzeldereense Bernhauer & Peks, 2013: 336 [unjustified emendation - Art. 19.1.]

According to the Art. 32.5.2.1. “In the case of a diacritic or other mark, the mark concerned is deleted”.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) karacaorenense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2012**

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) karacaorenense Bernhauer & Peks, 2012: 211 [wrong original spelling - Art. 11.2.]

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) karacaorenense Bernhauer & Peks, 2012: 336 [unjustified emendation - Art. 19.1.]

According to the Art. 32.5.2.1. “In the case of a diacritic or other mark, the mark concerned is deleted”.

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***Agapanthia dahli calculensis* Lazarev, 2013**

(Figs 12-13)

Agapanthia dahli calculensis Lazarev, 2013: 128 - "North-east Kazakhstan, Sibinka River, 49°40'27.56"N, 82°39'13.12"E".

The main character of *A. d. calculensis* Lazarev, 2013 is the total absence of antennal setae tufts in majority of specimens. The original description was illustrated by the biggest and brightest specimens with moderate antennal tufts on 3rd segments. The typical structure of 3rd segment without setae tuft is shown (Fig. 13).

New Records

Several new localities of very interesting *Dorcadion* were discovered by A. Rubenyan in 2011 and 2013 in Armenia.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) sisianense* Lazarev, 2009**

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) sisianense Lazarev, 2009: 210; 2011: 264, 289.

The taxon was described from one locality only: Armenia, Sisian pass, 39°30'N, 46°00'E, about 2 km westwards Gorajk. Now one more population was discovered in Syunik Area near Tekh (39°33'26''N, 46°28'30''E).

Materials. 2 males, Armenia, 4 km NW Tekh, 1622 m, 39°34'7''N 46°25'47''E, 15.05.2011, A. Rubenyan - MD; 3 males, 1 female, Armenia, Tekh, 1600 m, 39°34'6''N 46°25'52'' E, 03.05.2013, A. Rubenyan – MD, ML.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) megriense* Lazarev, 2009**

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) megriense Lazarev, 2009: 212; 2011: 264, 289.

The taxon was described from one locality only: Armenia, Megri ridge, 5-6 km N Shvanidzor, 38°59'N, 46°23'E. Now one more population was discovered: 10 km NEE Sisian, 2150 m, 39°32'54''N, 46°8'34''E.

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Materials. 4 males, 1 female, Armenia, 10 km NEE Sisian, 2150 m, 39°32'54''N, 46°8'34''E, 03.05.2013, A. Rubenyan - MD.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) laeve vladimiri* Danilevsky et Murzin, 2009**

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) laeve vladimiri Danilevsky et Murzin, 2009: 13.

The taxon was known up to now from Megri and Kafan districts of Armenia. Now one more population was discovered in Syunik Area near Tekh (39°33'26''N 46°28'30''E).

Materials. 2 males, 2 females, Armenia, 4 km NW Tekh, 1622 m, 39°34'7''N 46°25'47''E, 15.05.2011, A. Rubenyan - MD.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) indutum* Faldermann, 1837**

Dorcadion indutum Faldermann, 1837: 276.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) indutum, Danilevsky, 2010: 233 - "distributed near Goris and in Karabakh".

The taxon was known up to now from near Goris and from Karabakh. Now three more localities were discovered: 3 km SE Iskhanasar, 1902 m, 39°33'2''N 46°4'27''E; 3 km NW Hoznavar, 1902m, 39°38'1''N 46°19'15''E; Tekh, 1600 m, 39°34'6''N 46°25'52'' E.

Materilas. 11 males, 3 females, Armenia, 3 km SE Iskhanasar, 1902 m, 39°33'2.03''N 46°4'27.22''E, 14.05.2011, A. Rubenyan - MD; 8 males, 2 females, Armenia, 3 km NW Hoznavar, 1902 m, 39°38'0.81''N 46°19'14.99''E, 15.05.2011, A. Rubenyan - MD; 15 males, 5 females, Armenia, Tekh, 1600 m, 39°34'6''N 46°25'52'' E, 03.05.2013, A. Rubenyan - MD, ML.

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Figs 1-2. - *Brachyta variabilis shapovalovi*, **ssp. n.**: 1 - male, holotype; 2 - female, paratype: "Kaz. SSR, Kokpety, 500, 25.V.1989, leg. M. Danilevsky".

Figs 3-6. - *Anoplistes halodendri kasatkini*, **ssp. n.**: 3 - male, holotype; 4-6 - paratypes, Dagestan, Tlokh, 600 m, 3.6.1988, V.Karasev (4-5 - males, 6 - female).

Figs 7-8. - *Cleroclytus collaris savitskyi*, **ssp. n.**: 7 - male, holotype; 8 - female, paratype, Mongolia, Khovd aimak, Dod-Narujn, 26.6.2005, R. Yakovlev.

Fig 9. - *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium papayense*, **ssp. n.**: male, holotype;

Figs 10-11. - *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) gorbunovi rubenyani*, **ssp. n.**: 10 - male, holotype; 11 - female, paratype, "Armenia, 1 km S Svarantz, 1917 m, 39°21'13.39"N 46°12'44.21"E, 14.05.2011, A. Rubenyan".

Figs 12-13. *Agapanthia dahli calculensis* Lazarev, 2013: 12 - male, paratype, E Kazakhstan, 400 m, Ust-Kamenogorsk env., Sibinka River, Bazombai, 26.05.2003, M.Danilevsky; 13 - antenna.

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